

Aqueous Polymerization of Methyl Methacrylate Initiated by N-Bromosuccinimide—Reducing Metal Salt Redox Couple.

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Manuscript received 14 July 1976; revised 14 September 1976; accepted 12 January 1977

Polymerization of methyl methacrylate by N-bromosuccinimide/vanadyl sulfate as redox initiator in aqueous solutions has been studied. N-bromosuccinimide by itself cannot initiate polymerization in dark but, does so strongly in presence of reducing metal salts e.g., Fe^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Cu^+ , Ti^{3+} etc (in aqueous medium) even in dark. However, in presence of U.V. light N-bromosuccinimide can be used as a good initiator. The rate of polymerization under nitrogen atmosphere at $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ is proportional to the square-root of N-bromosuccinimide concentration (1.0×10^{-4} — 9.0×10^{-4} mol. l^{-1}) and proportional to the first power of monomer concentration (1.88×10^{-2} — 9.40×10^{-2} mol. l^{-1}) within the range studied.

However, the effect of activator concentration, VO_2^+ , on the polymerization rate shows an interesting trend. The polymerization rate shows an usual square-root dependence on the activator concentration within the range 1.0×10^{-4} — 5.0×10^{-4} mol. l^{-1} . But as the activator concentration is increased beyond 5×10^{-4} mol. l^{-1} , the polymerization rate becomes almost independent of the activator concentration. The overall activation energy is about 5.25 K. cal/mole. Inorganic electrolytes depress the rate of polymerization whereas an emulsifier enhances it. pH of the medium (neutral or acidic) does not have much influence on the polymerization rate down to the value of 4.00. However, at pH 3.00, the rate is decreased considerably. The polymer samples are characterized by the absence of hydroxyl, halogen and sulfate end groups. Polymerization through succinimidyl radical was suggested to account for the unusual end group profile. Based on our findings suitable mechanism of initiation and termination has been proposed.

N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE (I) (NBS) is known as a selective brominating agent and the reaction proceeds via free-radical intermediate. However, its use as an initiator of vinyl polymerization is only limited¹⁻³. Dannley et al¹ reported that at elevated temperatures (95-100°C) it catalyses the homopolymerization of methyl methacrylate (MMA) whereas under similar conditions it inhibits the homopolymerization of styrene. Later on, Otsu et al² reported the polymerization of both methyl methacrylate and styrene during their study on the effectiveness of (I) as a cocatalyst on the reduced-nickel initiated vinyl polymerization. Recently Bantia et al³⁻⁵ studied the use of several classes of N-halocompounds viz., N-haloamines, N-haloacetamide; N-halosuccinimide alone, or, as a component of redox initiating systems as initiator of vinyl polymerization.

The present work has been undertaken to study the kinetics of polymerization of methyl methacrylate in aqueous medium initiated by N-bromosuccinimide-vanadyl sulfate redox pair and also to help in elucidation of the mechanism of initiation and termination.

Experimental

Methyl methacrylate was purified by the usual procedure and stored at $0-5^\circ\text{C}$. Vanadyl sulfate (B.D.H.) (VO_2^+) was of analytical grade. N-Bromosuccinimide (B.D.H.) was purified by rapid crystallization from boiling water as described elsewhere⁷.

Aqueous polymerization of MMA was carried out under N_2 atmosphere in a pyrex conical flask (1.0 ml. volume) fitted with air-tight standard joint for passing N_2 and injecting other ingredients. Various ingredients were added in the following order: Vanadyl sulphate solution, monomer and N-bromosuccinimide solution in the flask containing requisite amount of water and placed in a thermostat. All operations being conducted under positive pressure of purified N_2 ⁸. The total time of deaeration was 15 minutes. Polymerization started immediately without any induction period and a stable sol or a colloidal phase remains throughout. Just at the end of the reaction time 15 ml. of alkaline hydroquinone solution (~1.5%) was added into the system to inhibit the reaction followed by the addition of neutral salt (MgSO_4) to break the colloidal phase.

The polymer was immediately filtered through a No. 4 Gooch Crucible and washed thoroughly with hot water. Subsequently, it was dried in a vacuum oven at 40-50°C overnight and then weighed and the percentage conversion was calculated. The results of the duplicate runs were generally within $\pm 0.5-1.0\%$ conversion.

The number of average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) of the polymer (PMMA-unfractionated) was determined viscometrically with benzene as the solvent by a Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer at 30°C. The viscometer was with large efflux times and negligible kinetic energy corrections and \bar{M}_n was calculated from the intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ using the following equation⁹

$$[\eta] = 8.69 \times 10^{-5} \bar{M}_n^{0.76} \quad \dots (1)$$

Results and Discussions

In presence of N-bromosuccinimide alone, no polymerization takes place in dark but occurs only in presence of U. V. light. When N-Bromosuccinimide in combination with various reducing metal salts, e.g., Fe^{2+} , VO^{2+} , Cu^+ , Ti^{3+} , is used as an initiator system, polymerization takes place almost instantaneously even in dark (Table-1). The polymerization was inhibited by hydroquinone, *p*-benzoquinone, 2-2 Diphenyl-1-1 picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and retarded effectively by atmospheric- O_2 indicating free-radical polymerization. It can also be mentioned here that this system shows only a weak polymerizability of styrene in aqueous (biphasic) medium, presumably due to its low solubility in water¹⁰.

TABLE 1—INITIATOR SYSTEMS INVOLVING N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE — REDUCING METAL IONS FOR AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION OF METHYL METHACRYLATE.

[MMA]— 9.4×10^{-2} mol. l.⁻¹, [NBS]— 1.0×10^{-3} mol. l.⁻¹, [ACTIVATOR]— 5×10^{-3} mol. l.⁻¹, TEMP.— $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$.

Serial No.	Activator	Induction Period in mins.	Polymerization Time in hours.	Percentage conversion
1.	None (in dark)	—	72	No Polymerization
2.	None (in U.V. (light))	15	3	~ 34.00
3.	VO^{2+}	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	~ 80.00
4.	VO^{2+} (in O_2 atm.)	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	~ 20.00
5.	VO^{2+} (in presence of various inhibitors)	—	72	No Polymerization
6.	Fe^{2+}	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	~ 46.00
7.	Ti^{3+}	0	$\frac{1}{2}$	~ 40.00
8.	Cu^+	0	2	~ 35.00

Rate Dependence on Catalyst Concentration (N-Bromosuccinimide)— The effect of N-bromosuccinimide at a fixed concentration of MMA, viz., 0.094 mol.l.⁻¹ and a fixed concentration of vanadyl sulfate viz., 1×10^{-3} mol.l.⁻¹ has been shown in Fig-1. The rate of polymerization (R_p) is found to increase with increasing concentration of N-bromosuccinimide. The

plot of R_p , as measured from steady state zone square-root of N-bromosuccinimide concentration yields a linear graph showing the half-order dependence on the catalyst concentration (Fig-2). The variation of molecular weight also shows the normal behaviour, i.e., the molecular weight decreases with the increase of catalyst concentration. (Fig-3).

Fig. 1. Yield-Time Curve in aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate at $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ using 1×10^{-3} mol. l.⁻¹ $[\text{VO}_5\text{O}_4]$, 9.4×10^{-2} mol. l.⁻¹ $[\text{MMA}]$ and varying $[\text{NBS}]$.

Fig. 2. R_p versus square-root of initiator (catalyst and activator) concentration (in mol. l.⁻¹).

Fig. 3. Log-log plot of number-average molecular weight (\bar{M}_n) against initiator (catalyst and activator) concentration (in mol. l.⁻¹).

Rate Dependence on Activator Concentration (Vanadyl Sulfate)—The effect of vanadyl sulfate at a fixed monomer concentration (0.094 mol.l.⁻¹), at a fixed N-bromosuccinimide concentration (1×10^{-3} mol.l.⁻¹) has been shown in Fig.4. The rate dependence on the activator concentration is interesting and unusual. In the concentration range 1.0×10^{-4} – 5.0×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹ R_p , as measured from steady state zone is found to increase steadily with the activator concentration. However, further increase in the activator concentration does not appear to have an appreciable effect on R_p . R_p when plotted against the square-root of the activator concentration gives a curve as shown in Fig-2. A linear graph upto to the activator concentration 5×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹ shows a half-order dependence on the activator concentration within this range. However, even a further ten-fold increase in

the activator concentration does not appear to have any appreciable effect on R_p . The same conclusion can also be drawn from the fact that the activator concentration beyond 5×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹ does not appreciably change the average molecular weight of the polymer (Fig-3). The rate equation in fact, may be represented by

$$R_p = k[\text{NBS}]^{0.5} [\text{VOSO}_4]^x [\text{MMA}]^{1.0} \quad \dots (2)$$

where x changes from 0.5 to zero as the concentration of the vanadyl sulfate is increased beyond 5×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹ at a fixed catalyst and monomer concentration. This behaviour of vanadyl sulfate is quite in contrast with the normal free-radical polymerization involving mutual bimolecular termination of polymer radical, according to which the rate should vary as the square-root of the concentration of both the reactants¹¹⁻¹⁵. It appears from this study that either the rate of radical generation in this system becomes almost independent of the vanadyl sulfate concentration when it exceeds 5×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹ or, the increase of vanadyl sulfate concentration increases the ionic strength of the medium leading to incipient coagulation which brings down the number of polymer particles thereby affecting the rate of polymerization. Moreover, the oxidative, or, reductive terminations of polymethyl methacrylate radicals by polyvalent ions likely to be present in the system cannot be ruled out¹⁶.

Rate Dependence on Monomer Concentration—Variation of the rate of polymerization with monomer concentration at $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and at a fixed concentration of N-bromosuccinimide (7.5×10^{-4} mol.l.⁻¹) and vanadyl sulfate (1×10^{-3} mol.l.⁻¹) are shown in Fig-5. Log R_p and log [MMA] are related linearly as shown in Fig-6. The linear relationship is somewhat unusual. Conflicting results are available in the literature regarding the effect of monomer concentration on the rate of

Fig. 4. Yield Time Curve in aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate at $40 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ using 1×10^{-3} mol. l.⁻¹ [NBS], 9.4×10^{-3} mol. l.⁻¹ [MMA] and varying $[\text{VOSO}_4]$.

polymerization of water soluble vinyl monomers¹⁷⁻²¹. For aqueous polymerization of MMA by the redox pair KMnO_4 -oxalic acid, it has been reported that with increasing monomer concentration the rate increases linearly, passes through a maxima and then decreases, passes through a minima and then rises again¹⁷. Similar observation was also made by several workers^{18,19}. However, linear variation of R_p on

monomer concentration was observed for aqueous polymerization of MMA initiated by Fe^{2+} - BrO_3^- redox couple²⁰. This linear relationship suggests the termination rate to be proportional to the monomer concentration in the aqueous phase. Moreover, the monomer exponent is found to be unity. For a monomer such as MMA having a higher affinity for its insoluble polymer than for water, the general observation is of a first-order dependence of rate on the initial monomer concentration²¹.

Fig. 5. Yield-Time Curve in aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate at $40 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ using 1×10^{-3} mol. l^{-1} $[\text{VOSO}_4]$, 7.5×10^{-4} mol. l^{-1} $[\text{NBS}]$ and varying $[\text{MMA}]$.

Fig. 6. Log-log plot of R_p against monomer concentration (in mol. l^{-1}).

Rate Dependence on Temperature—Any increase in polymerization temperature is accompanied by an increase in R_p , as expected from Arrhenius Theory. The overall activation energy (E_a) has been graphically calculated in the temperature range 30 – 50° from the Arrhenius plot of $\log R_p$ against $1/T^\circ\text{K}$. Any further rise in the reaction temperature is associated with a visible change in the physical nature of the aqueous polymerization media from sol or colloidal phase to precipitative phase, which are likely to affect the rate of polymerization²¹. Studies at higher temperature ($>50^\circ$) have not therefore been undertaken. Several workers reported similar observations that coagulating effect of heat are prone to decrease the R_p considerably and attributed it to the more facile mutual termination of growing polyradical chains^{20,21}. However for the same monomer, the limiting temperature after which R_p begins to decrease, is also dependent on the rate of the initiating reaction and hence will not be the same for different initiating systems²¹. We might mention here that the reported fall in R_p above 45° for aqueous polymerization of MMA by $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ - $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_4$ ^{20,21} is in error when rechecked with the original reference²².

The value of overall activation energy (E_a) is about 5.25 K. cal/mole. For aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate the E_a value obtained using this redox system is rather low as compared to other redox systems studied^{17,20-24}. This can only be attributed to the low energy of activation of the parent redox system, as energy of activation of other reactions of interest viz., initiation, propagation and chain-termination is fixed for polymerization of any monomer (here MMA) in aqueous phase. Moreover, from the above kinetic studies, participation of other radical (initiating)-destroying side reactions which may also lower the E_a value can be ruled out. However, due to non-availability of the necessary data for the energy of activation of the system VO^{2+} -NBS, no comparison can be made with our results. Another possibility for the low E_a value, of the polymerization reaction is the probable increase of incipient coagulation due to the temperature rise, which will tend to bring down the polymerization rate caused by the lowering of the number of polymer particles. Thus, the resultant increase of the rate of polymerization (R_p) will be somewhat less than what it normally should have been. This will certainly lead to the lowering of E_a value. Furthermore, this effect is more pronounced for heterogeneous aqueous phase polymerization initiated by redox system containing metal ions as one of the components because these metal ions enhance incipient coagulation^{20,24}.

Effect of Different Additives on Rate of Polymerization-

(A) *Effect of Emulsifier (sodium lauryl sulfate) on R_p* : Aqueous polymerization of methyl methacrylate results in the formation of a colloidal stabilized swollen polymer—monomer phase. Any such factor which can increase the stability of the colloidal phase will undoubtedly increase the rate of polymerization. The stability of the colloidal phase will increase proportionally due to the addition of an emulsifier. Furthermore, increase of soap concentration will increase the number of polymer particles or, in other words the number of reaction sites and so the net result would be an increase in R_p . The present study also confirms the above idea as is quite evident from Table-2. With increasing concentration of sodium lauryl sulfate R_p increases considerably, as observed by several group of workers²¹.

(B) *Effect of Inorganic Electrolytes on R_p* : Addition of large quantities of inorganic electrolytes decrease the rate of polymerization (Table-2). Polyvalent cation (Mg^{2+}) is more effective in bringing down the R_p than the monovalent cation (Na^+)²¹. The higher efficiency of polyvalent ions must be attributed to their stronger coagulating power (Schulz-Hardy Rule). Moreover, the decrease of R_p is inversely proportional to the increase of the electrolyte concentration. This is attributed to the fact that the increase of concentration of these electrolytes results in a parallel increase of the ionic strength of the medium, with more pronounced coagulating effect²¹.

(C) *Effect of pH on R_p* : Polymerization can not be effected in alkaline medium. With increasing acid concentration, the R_p remains more or less unchanged within the pH range 7.00 to 4.00 (Table-2). Probably upto this range the rate decrease due to coagulating effect of the added acid and the rate increase due to the increased acidity of the medium balance each other

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDITIVES ON THE RATE OF POLYMERIZATION (R_p).

Additives	Concentration	$R_p \times 10^4$ mol. l. ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹
(1) NaCl	0.0	6.11
	0.01%	5.63
	0.05%	4.06
(2) $MgSO_4$	0.01%	5.06
(3) Sodium lauryl sulfate	0.0	6.11
	1×10^{-5} mol. l. ⁻¹	7.81
	5×10^{-4} mol. l. ⁻¹	9.85
(4) H_2SO_4	<u>pH</u>	
	7.00	6.11
	5.00	6.49
	4.00	6.01
	3.00	4.10

and R_p remains practically unchanged. Below this range at pH 3.00, however, the coagulating effect of the acid becomes predominant and a perceptible decrease in R_p is observed.

Effect of Conversion on the Intrinsic Viscosity [η] It has been claimed by some workers^{17,25-27} that in heterogeneous aqueous polymerization the intrinsic viscosity [η] tend to increase with increase of conversion and attains a steady value. The effect of conversion on [η] has been studied very carefully (Table-3). It appears from the study that in contrast to the above mentioned behaviour, here, [η] does not change appreciably with change of conversion.

TABLE 3—VARIATION OF THE INTRINSIC VISCOSITY [η] WITH CONVERSION IN A RUN. [MMA]— 9.4×10^{-2} mol. l.⁻¹, Temperature— $40 \pm 0.1^\circ C$.

Serial No.	[NBS] $\times 10^4$ mol. l. ⁻¹	[VOSO ₄] $\times 10^4$ mol. l. ⁻¹	Percentage conversion	[η]
1	10.00	20.00	7.34	0.760
			18.25	0.766
			31.60	0.765
			51.84	0.766
2	10.00	5.00	16.56	0.864
			30.56	0.860
			50.93	0.864
			60.20	0.865
			20.00	0.720
			32.27	0.715
3	8.00	10.00	49.97	0.720
			57.51	0.720
			10.30	1.455
			14.06	1.450
4	2.50	10.00	22.82	1.455
			25.41	1.455

Mechanism: It appears from the dependence of the rate of polymerization on initiator concentrations that a free-radical mechanism is operative here. Similar conclusions can be drawn from the fact that the conventional free-radical inhibitors viz., hydroquinone, *p*-benzoquinone and DPPH either inhibit or, retard the reaction appreciably (as already mentioned). Moreover the retarding effect of O_2 has also been observed. However, it is worth emphasizing here that although free-radical chain nature of the reactions of N-bromosuccinimide are well known, there is still doubt as to the nature of the actual chain carriers. Bloomfield²⁸ suggested a mechanism based on succinimidyl radical being the chain carrier whereas Goldfinger^{28,29} visualised that N-bromosuccinimide act only as a source of molecular bromine in low concentrations suggesting bromine atom radical as the actual chain carrier. As polymer end group characterization provides a convenient method for establishing the nature of such intermediate free-radicals participating in the initiation reaction some purified polymer samples were subjected to dye partition test for characterization of the end groups^{4,31,32} incorporated in them. Both bromine and hydroxyl end groups were found to be absent, which ruled out the possibility of hydroxyl and halogen radicals as the initiating free-radical in the present case.

